

The Disciplinary Diversity Shrinkage—The Experience of Colombian Social Science Research Groups

Julián D. Cortés¹ and Emanuel Kulczycki²

julian.cortess@urosario.edu.co

¹School of Management and Business, Universidad del Rosario, Autopista Norte Cl. 200, Bogotá (Colombia)

emanuel.kulczycki@amu.edu.pl

²Scholarly Communication Research Group, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań (Poland)

Abstract

This study focuses on measuring the disciplinary diversity within Colombian social science (SS) research groups, a context that has received limited attention in existing literature dominated by analyses of STEM disciplines in high-income countries. Using data from MinCiencias' national assessments (2013–2021), we applied the *DIV* diversity index to measure variety, balance, and disparity in 1,105 SS research groups. Our findings reveal a decline in disciplinary diversity over time, particularly among top-ranked groups, while lower-ranked groups maintained more stable, though less diverse, disciplinary profiles. We argue that increasing size and hierarchy of top-tier groups may hinder the inclusion of diverse expertise among their members. These findings highlight the need for policy reforms in research assessment systems. Future research should expand to other disciplines and countries, leveraging open bibliometric data to explore diversity's role in shaping research outputs and impacts.

Introduction

Is a science team or research group cognitively diverse? How to measure its disciplinary diversity? Science teams and research groups have emerged as crucial drivers in scientific discoveries (Wu et al., 2019; Wuchty et al., 2007). Understanding science teams and research groups' interdisciplinary factors and related assessment measurements is part of the current agenda of science of team science (SciTS) (Li et al., 2023). A rich research agenda on this topic has explored various dimensions, including team size, multidisciplinary, knowledge diversity, interdisciplinary collaboration, and sociodemographic factors (Aydinoglu et al., 2016; Bercovitz & Feldman, 2011; Huo et al., 2019; Perović et al., 2016; Roelofs et al., 2019; Skilton, 2009; Wang et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2019; Xie et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2012).

Despite significant advancements on understanding the diversity of teams and research groups, most studies heavily rely on international citation databases such as Web of Science and Scopus or USPTO for patents, which may not accurately capture the research trends in various contexts where the involvement of authors from low-income countries is significantly low (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016). Moreover, they primarily focus on high-income countries and Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics, and Medicine (STEMM) disciplines, which, in contrast to middle-low-income countries, have macro advantages in terms of scientific infrastructure and science policies (Abramo & D'Angelo, 2024; Cortés & Ramírez Cajiao, 2024; Kulczycki et al., 2018; Vasen et al., 2023).

With this in mind, this research in progress aims to measure the disciplinary diversity of research groups of social science (SS) in Colombia across 2013–2021. We focus on Colombia, a country that—despite limited infrastructure and financial resources allocated to science—achieves notable levels of scientific output, demonstrating efficiency and resilience under resource constraints (Cortés & Ramírez Cajiao, 2024). In doing so, we contribute to the literature on interdisciplinary factors and related assessment measurements of SciTS in the domain of SS in middle-low-income countries.

Methodology

Materials

We used the open access data sets curated by the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation of Colombia (MinCiencias) (MinCiencias, 2023). The data sets contain information on the national assessments conducted in 2013, 2014, 2015, 2017, 2019, and 2021. Our analysis will incorporate two data sets: the research groups and the national assessments results (MinCiencias, 2022a, 2022b).

Colombian science policies defined research groups as (MinCiencias, 2021, p. 22): “The basic modern unit for generating scientific knowledge and its application to technological development, comprising individuals from one or more disciplines and institutions who synergistically work together around a specific field of knowledge.” (Own translation). Research groups, as formal academic units within a school or department, comprise a defined number of affiliated researchers, generally hired, united by a shared research direction, and led by one or more directors.

The classification system for research groups is based on a ranking structure. There are four ranks: A1, A, B, and C. A1 is the highest rank. The ranks are determined by considering research outputs, collaboration networks, and contributions to the scientific community. There is also an additional rank called '*Reconocido*' (Recognized). This rank is given to groups that have participated in the annual call and have been acknowledged by MinCiencias, but have not yet achieved any of the other classifications (MinCiencias, 2021).

Researchers are responsible for detailing their disciplinary expertise in their research portfolios and products on the national platform (CvLAC), which includes their specific disciplines and fields of expertise. The institution and research groups oversee this process. The classification of both groups and researchers within disciplinary grand areas and disciplines by MinCiencias is based on the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) fields of science (FOS) normalization framework (OECD, 2015).

Methods

We implemented the *DIV* diversity indicator proposed by Leydesdorff et al. (2019) which is based on the Rao-Stirling diversity index (Porter & Rafols, 2009; Stirling, 2007) with certain adjustments. *DIV* evaluates the three aspects of diversity (i.e., variety, balance, disparity) before merging them and it meets monotonicity, therefore this index meets most of the proper qualities of logical structure and validations of interdisciplinarity research (Zwanenburg et al., 2022). We adjusted *DIV* components for interdisciplinary research among diverse research groups.

Variety refers to the number of different disciplines in a research group. This is measured as *Relative variety (RV)*. We formalized as follows:

$$RV = \frac{n_d}{N_d}$$

Where n_d is the number of distinct disciplines in the group and N_d is the total number of distinct disciplines across all groups.

Balance reflects the evenness of distribution of researchers across disciplines within each research group. We measured this via *Gini coefficient (G)*. We formalize as follows:

$$G = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n |x_i - x_j|}{2n^2 \bar{x}}$$

Where x_i is the number of researchers in discipline i , and n is the total number of disciplines in a research group.

Disparity refers to the conceptual distance between researchers disciplines within the group. We computed this via *Average disparity (AD)*. To achieve this, we computed the cosine similarity (Zwanenburg et al., 2022), as follows:

- Co-occurrence matrix of disciplines:

We assembled a discipline matrix, where rows represent different groups and columns disciplines.

Each matrix cell, denoted as $x_{g,d}$, represents the number of researchers in group g affiliated with discipline d .

Based on the discipline matrix, we assembled a co-occurrence matrix where rows and columns represent disciplines.

Each entry $M_{i,j}$ in the matrix indicates the total number of times disciplines i and j co-occur across all research groups:

$$M_{i,j} = \sum_g (x_{g,i} \times x_{g,j})$$

Where $x_{g,i}$ and $x_{g,j}$ are the counts of researchers in group g for disciplines i and j , respectively.

- Calculating cosine similarity:

- For disciplines i and j , the cosine similarity is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Cosine similarity } (i,j) = \frac{\sum_g (x_{g,i} \times x_{g,j})}{\sqrt{\sum_g (x_{g,i})^2} \times \sqrt{\sum_g (x_{g,j})^2}}$$

The numerator is the co-occurrence of disciplines i and j across all groups and the denominator normalizes by the product of the magnitudes of the discipline vectors.

- Convert cosine similarity to disparity:

- Disparity between disciplines i and j , is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Disparity}(i,j) = 1 - \text{Cosine similarity}(i,j)$$

- Aggregating disparity for each research group:

- For each research group with n distinct disciplines, we use the calculated the AD as:

$$AD = \frac{\sum_{i \neq j} \text{Disparity}(i,j)}{n \cdot (n - 1)}$$

The numerator sums the pair-wise disparities among all distinct discipline pairs within the group and the denominator represents the total number of unique discipline pairs, ensuring the average is taken correctly.

Finally, we calculate the DIV for each research group as follows:

$$DIV = RV \times (1 - G) \times AD$$

We measure DIV on a sub-sample of 1105 multidisciplinary groups (i.e., groups composed of researchers from two or more different disciplines, a required condition for applying the DIV) classified only in the grand area of SS across the periods analysed with at least three members.

Results and discussion

Figure 1 reports the average DIV for research groups by rank with longitudinal consistency (i.e., those which were ranked in all periods). Overall, top-tier groups showed longitudinal consistency, yet a decreasing trend in average DIV . Rank A groups display the most consistent longitudinal performance, indicating that these top-tier groups maintain their high standing over time. While Rank A1 demonstrates consistency, it's slightly less consistent than Rank A. Rank B and C groups exhibit moderate levels of consistency. The "Recognized" group exhibited the least consistent performance, especially after 2015, likely due to high turnover and instability within this lower-ranking tier. While initially similar to Rank A groups, Rank A1 groups exhibit a decrease in average DIV after 2015, reaching their lowest point in 2017 before levelling off.

A notable decline in performance was observed within Rank B groups from 2013 to 2017, with an uptick in subsequent years. Rank C groups exhibit relatively stable average *DIV*, with minor fluctuations occurring in 2017 and 2019. Rank Recognized groups, characterized by consistently low average *DIV*.

The analysis of disciplinary diversity (*DIV*) revealed a notable decline in interdisciplinarity over time, especially among top-ranked research groups. In contrast, lower-ranked groups demonstrated more stability in diversity, though their overall levels of interdisciplinarity remained lower. Casually, top-ranked groups are those with the larger team size. For instance, A1 groups had 6.3 members in average in 2013 to a peak of ~12 in 2019, followed by a slight decline to ~11 in 2021, whereas Recognized rank showed relatively consistent values, peaking at ~4 in 2019 before declining slightly to ~3 in 2021 (Cortés & Kulczycki, 2024). Therefore, we argue that flattened team structures —characterized by reduced size and hierarchy— have been showed to surpass larger, hierarchical organizations in generating innovative knowledge. This decisive factor might be attributed to their capacity to cultivate novel combinations of ideas, encourage equal participation, and provide expanded leadership opportunities (Wu et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2022). Concerning national science policy, the last research group call issued in 2021 and 275 pages long, has no core mention of the importance of *diversity-interdisciplinarity* in the assessment, either in the productivity nor their group’s composition (MinCiencias, 2021). The lack of a national directive could lead to a disregard for interdisciplinary research and diverse disciplinary composition.

Figure 1 Average DIV of research groups with longitudinal consistency.

Conclusions

This research in progress aimed to measure the disciplinary diversity of research groups of social science (SS) in Colombia across 2013-2021. The findings revealed a decline in diversity, particularly among top-ranked groups, while lower-ranked groups exhibited more stable but less diverse compositions. We discussed these findings with previous studies arguing that smaller, flat-structured teams were identified as more innovative, fostering equitable participation and novel ideas, whereas the growing size and hierarchical nature of top-tier groups may undermine their long-term scientific standing. These insights are relevant beyond Colombia, as other middle- and low-income countries with similar evaluation frameworks may face comparable challenges in promoting diversity and interdisciplinarity. This aligns with global efforts, such as DORA and CoARA, advocating for research assessment reforms to better

capture collaboration, interdisciplinarity, and societal impact. However, the study's focus on group member diversity, rather than research outputs or impacts, and its confinement to SS in a single country, limit its scope. Future research should expand to other disciplines and countries, leveraging open-access bibliometric databases like OpenAlex and Dimensions to explore diversity in research outputs and their impacts across multiple contexts.

Acknowledgments

References

- Abramo, G., & D'Angelo, C. A. (2024). The scientific standing of nations and its relationship with economic competitiveness. *PLOS ONE*, *19*(6), e0304299. <https://doi.org/10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0304299>
- Aydinoglu, A. U., Allard, S., & Mitchell, C. (2016). Measuring diversity in disciplinary collaboration in research teams: An ecological perspective. *Research Evaluation*, *25*(1), 18–36. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvv028>
- Bercovitz, J., & Feldman, M. (2011). The mechanisms of collaboration in inventive teams: Composition, social networks, and geography. *Research Policy*, *40*(1), 81–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2010.09.008>
- Cortés, J. D., & Kulczycki, E. (2024). *The Colombian Kaleidoscope—Interlinking Interdisciplinary Diversity of Scientists in Social Sciences Research Groups and Scientific Status*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14179861>
- Cortés, J. D., & Ramírez Cajiao, M. C. (2024). The policy is dead, long live the policy—Revealing science, technology, and innovation policy priorities and government transitions via network analysis. *Quantitative Science Studies*, *5*(2), 317–331. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00295
- Huo, D., Motohashi, K., & Gong, H. (2019). Team diversity as dissimilarity and variety in organizational innovation. *Research Policy*, *48*(6), 1564–1572. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2019.03.020>
- Kulczycki, E., Engels, T. C. E., Pölönen, J., Bruun, K., Dušková, M., Guns, R., Nowotniak, R., Petr, M., Sivertsen, G., Istenič Starčič, A., & Zuccala, A. (2018). Publication patterns in the social sciences and humanities: evidence from eight European countries. *Scientometrics*, *116*(1), 463–486. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-018-2711-0>
- Leydesdorff, L., Wagner, C. S., & Bornmann, L. (2019). Interdisciplinarity as diversity in citation patterns among journals: Rao-Stirling diversity, relative variety, and the Gini coefficient. *Journal of Informetrics*, *13*(1), 255–269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2018.12.006>
- Li, R., Guns, R., Engels, T. C. E., Zhang, L., & Huang, Y. (2023). Tracking the featured topics of the International Science of Team Science conference series and their evolution during 2010–2019. *Scientometrics*, *128*(4), 2447–2469. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11192-023-04651-3/METRICS>
- MinCiencias. (2021). *Convocatoria nacional para el reconocimiento y medición de grupos de investigación, desarrollo tecnológico o de innovación y para el reconocimiento de investigadores del Sistema Nacional de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación*. <https://minciencias.gov.co/convocatorias/fortalecimiento-capacidades-para-la-generacion-conocimiento/convocatoria-nacional-para>
- MinCiencias. (2022a). *Grupos de Investigación Reconocidos*. Grupos de Investigación Reconocidos | Datos Abiertos Colombia. <https://www.datos.gov.co/Ciencia-Tecnolog-a-e-Innovaci-n/Grupos-de-Investigaci-n-Reconocidos/hrhc-c4wu>
- MinCiencias. (2022b, September 25). *Investigadores reconocidos por convocatoria*. Investigadores Reconocidos Por Convocatoria. <https://bit.ly/3MKGgyE>

- MinCiencias. (2023). *La Ciencia en Cifras*. <https://minciencias.gov.co/la-ciencia-en-cifras>
- Mongeon, P., & Paul-Hus, A. (2016). The journal coverage of Web of Science and Scopus: a comparative analysis. *Scientometrics*, *106*(1), 213–228. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1765-5>
- OECD. (2015). *Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for Collecting and Reporting Data on Research and Experimental Development* (The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities). OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264239012-EN>
- Perović, S., Radovanović, S., Sikimić, V., & Berber, A. (2016). Optimal research team composition: data envelopment analysis of Fermilab experiments. *Scientometrics*, *108*(1), 83–111. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-1947-9>
- Porter, A. L., & Rafols, I. (2009). Is science becoming more interdisciplinary? Measuring and mapping six research fields over time. *Scientometrics*, *81*(3), 719–745. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11192-008-2197-2/METRICS>
- Roelofs, S., Edwards, N., Viehbeck, S., & Anderson, C. (2019). Formative, embedded evaluation to strengthen interdisciplinary team science: Results of a 4-year, mixed methods, multi-country case study. *Research Evaluation*, *28*(1), 37–50. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvy023>
- Skilton, P. F. (2009). Does the human capital of teams of natural science authors predict citation frequency? *Scientometrics*, *78*(3), 525–542. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-007-1953-z>
- Stirling, A. (2007). A general framework for analysing diversity in science, technology and society. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, *4*(15), 707–719. <https://doi.org/10.1098/RSIF.2007.0213>
- Vasen, F., Sarthou, N. F., Romano, S. A., Gutiérrez, B. D., & Pintos, M. (2023). Turning academics into researchers: The development of National Researcher Categorization Systems in Latin America. *Research Evaluation*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/RESEVAL/RVAD021>
- Wang, C.-C., Lin, J.-T., Chen, D.-Z., & Lo, S.-C. (2023). A New Look at National Diversity of Inventor Teams within Organizations. *Journal of Informetrics*, *17*(1), 101369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2022.101369>
- Wu, L., Wang, D., & Evans, J. A. (2019). Large teams develop and small teams disrupt science and technology. *Nature*, *566*(7744), 378–382. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-0941-9>
- Wuchty, S., Jones, B. F., & Uzzi, B. (2007). The Increasing Dominance of Teams in Production of Knowledge. *Science*, *316*(5827), 1036–1039. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1136099>
- Xie, L., Zhou, J., Zong, Q., & Lu, Q. (2020). Gender diversity in R&D teams and innovation efficiency: Role of the innovation context☆. *Research Policy*, *49*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2019.103885>
- Xu, F., Wu, L., & Evans, J. (2022). Flat teams drive scientific innovation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *119*(23), e2200927119. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2200927119>
- Zhou, Q., Rousseau, R., Yang, L., Yue, T., & Yang, G. (2012). A general framework for describing diversity within systems and similarity between systems with applications in informetrics. *Scientometrics*, *93*(3), 787–812. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-012-0767-9>
- Zwanenburg, S., Nakhoda, M., & Whigham, P. (2022). Toward greater consistency and validity in measuring interdisciplinarity: a systematic and conceptual evaluation. *Scientometrics*, *127*(12), 7769–7788. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04310-z>